

The Influence of Shared Course Enrollments on Student Performance

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Abstract

Many factors influence whether or not undergraduate students complete their degree programs. Students who have many courses in common with other students have a high connectivity level, which we hypothesize will positively influence students' grades and persistence towards graduation. We use connectivity, as quantified by the frequency of shared courses between students, to measure how connected students in a degree program are to one another. Narrowing our population to Physics and Statistics majors at the Rochester Institute of Technology (RIT), we created adjacency matrices to represent connectivity levels across these students and compared these levels to their academic success. We studied the impact of student connectivity on GPA and graduation rate. Here we performed a logistic regression to test the relationship between connectivity and academic performance. While GPA seems to be weakly related to connectivity, our findings indicate a positive association between connectivity and likelihood of graduating. Educational institutions may find this information useful because clustering students together in classes would likely be linked to more students' completing their degree.

1 Introduction

Student retention in STEM is crucial to maintain readiness for entering the workforce. In today's world, there is an increasing need for workers in STEM related jobs. In fact, "the number of jobs requiring substantial STEM expertise has grown nearly 34% over the past decade" (Boggs et al., 2023). According to Boggs et al., part of this is a result of the coronavirus pandemic lockdowns with labor shortages becoming an extreme problem, specifically in technology. More than ever student retention and success in education should be the aim of technological institutions.

What this means is that we need to investigate the influences of retention further to understand what contributes to an increase in retention. By increasing retention, there is ultimately an increase in graduation rate. Student preparation is not the only proxy for retention that should be considered. According to a study done by Radunzel et al., student interest in STEM leads to a higher likelihood in persistence and obtaining a STEM degree (2015). Benish found that increasing representation and diversity in STEM will increase talent and reduce the urgent need for workers in this field (2018). Previous research performed logistic regression to study certain factors, such as the presence of undergraduate learning assistants, that affect failure rates (Alzen et al., 2018). For our study, we decided to look into student connectivity as a proxy for retention in STEM by visualizing the effects of students' shared classes on graduation based on gender and first generation (FG) versus continuing generation (CG). We performed logistic regression to assess the effect connectivity had on graduation rates at RIT.

Retention relates to these factors because connectivity is related to active learning. Lessons that involve student collaboration and discussion where students are more engaged are examples of active learning. According to Freeman et al., their research findings revealed "active learning increases student performance across the STEM disciplines" (Freeman et al., 2014). Grunspan et al. (2017) claims that Social Network Analysis, allows us to assess the impacts of learning relationships in the classroom. Similarly, we examined the effects of student relationships in

STEM by analyzing connectivity that was normalized based on course size. Students in smaller courses presumably benefit more from active learning because they are more likely to benefit from connectedness and engagement with other students. In our analysis, we normalized the measurement for connectivity to take into account the higher reward for connected students in smaller course sizes.

The present work fills the gap of what influences retention by investigating student connectivity. We examined how connectivity influences retention and success for certain groups of students. We used logistic regression to understand the influence connectivity had on the probability of graduating within 4 years. We also looked into connectivity as a proxy for academic preparedness by comparing levels of connectivity across a distribution of GPA levels.

2 Methods

2.1 Subsetting Data

We had access to a sample of almost a decade of data from 2013 to 2021 from RIT, that included all majors. Therefore, we decided to narrow our analysis down to specific majors and school terms. We were also curious specifically in STEM majors, and how connectivity benefits these students. We chose Physics and Statistics majors entering RIT in 2013 to 2015 to investigate and compare connectivity. We chose these cohort terms specifically since we wanted to study a subset that graduated before COVID in 2020. To control for variation due to major size, we included Applied Mathematics along with Applied Statistics, because these majors are similar and have some overlapping courses. After considering the 4 year and 6 year graduation rates, there is essentially no difference between the two results, so we will be examining at 4 year graduation rates. We looked specifically at subsets of first generation vs continuing generation students as well as male vs non-male subsets within those majors and cohort terms. One limitation is our broad classification of non-male students. We refer to students as “non-male” because that was how the data was recorded.

	Physics subset	Statistics/Mathematics subset
Total	79 students	155 students
Continuing/First Gen.	61/18	108/47
Male/Non-male	67/12	91/64

Table 1. Sample sizes of students separated by major and predictors (male vs non-male and continuing vs first generation).

2.2 Quantifying Students' Connectivity

The measurement we chose for connectivity was a normalized measurement of shared classes between two students. The normalized amount is calculated by taking the number of shared courses between each pair of students and dividing that by the total number of students in each specific course in the shared courses list. We created a connectivity matrix, where each entry is the normalized connectivity number for each pair of students.

Equation used for normalizing connectivity: $C_{ij} = \sum_{c \in S} \frac{1}{|c|}$

- Where S = set of shared courses between students i and j , and $|c|$ is the number of students enrolled in course c
- E.g. If student i and student j share $S = 3$ courses where one course has $|c| = 20$ students, one has $|c| = 25$ students, and the other contains $|c| = 30$, then their connectivity would be $1/20 + 1/25 + 1/30 = 0.123$

We then summed up the rows in the connectivity matrices (one for physics, one for stat/math) for each student to obtain their individual connectivity measurements.

2.3 Data Analysis

The histograms represent the distribution of the high and low connectivity values across GPA levels. The calculations for each major were done by setting high connectivity to represent values greater than or equal to the median and setting low connectivity to be values smaller than the median. Then, the odds ratio was calculated to find the odds of being highly connected when GPA is high (greater than or equal to 3.0).

Calculation of odds ratio:

High connectivity count = $\sum(\text{greater than or equal to median and GPA} \geq 3.0)$

Low connectivity count = $\sum(\text{less than the median and GPA} \geq 3.0)$

High connectivity odds = $\frac{\text{High connectivity count}}{\text{Low connectivity count}}$

Low connectivity odds = $\frac{\text{Low connectivity count}}{\text{High connectivity count}}$

Odds ratio = $\frac{\text{High connectivity odds}}{\text{Low connectivity odds}}$

2.4 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is a type of analysis that finds the correlation between predictor variables and the response variable, which is binary (yes or no, success or failure). This correlation is used to calculate the odds ratio ($\frac{p}{1-p}$), where p is the probability of a student graduating within 4 years, and predict the likelihood of the response variable based on the predictors. In this case connectivity was our predictor variable and graduation within 4 years was our response. The logistic regression analysis gave us a better understanding of factors that are linked to graduation rate. We used the following regression equation for analyzing the predicted probabilities for the groups (first generation vs continuing generation as well as male vs non-male), for Physics and Math/Stat majors:

Logistic Regression equation: **Graduate = Connectivity(X) + Intercept**

$$\frac{p}{1-p} = e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{\text{Connectivity}}}$$

- Where β_0 = intercept, β_1 = coefficient, and $x_{\text{Connectivity}}$ = connectivity measurement

While there were a few predictors we could have looked into, we decided to only look at first-generation (FG) vs continuing generation (CG) students and male vs non-male students. We would have included AALANA (African American, Latin American, and Native American) students because the data on AALANA was too limited. Interpreting these results by comparing underrepresented students to those commonly represented in STEM fields is important because it highlights potential barriers to success for marginalized students.

We used p-values to check for significance between connectivity and graduation likelihood for each group of students. The significance level we decided to use was 0.05, so we interpret a p-value below 0.05 as significant. We also looked at the 95% confidence intervals for each of the groups. We calculated these intervals by using these formulas:

Lower Bound = Predicted Probability – 1.96 × Standard Error

Upper Bound = Predicted Probability + 1.96 × Standard Error

3 Results

3.1 Connectivity in majors

Figure 1: Superimposed density histograms of connectivity for Stat/Math and Physics majors

The range of connectivity within the physics subset is 0.53 - 3.25 and within the stat/math subset is 0 - 4.03 after normalization. The physics majors have a unimodal distribution centering around a mid-range connectivity level. Because the physics major group only contains that major, there are likely many students taking the same required courses. This is why their connectivity would be more similar compared to stat/math, since stat/math includes two different majors in the sample.

3.2 Relationship Between Connectivity and Student Success

To assign the values that were considered high and low connectivity, we set all values greater than or equal to the median rows sums (of the connectivity matrix) as high connectivity, and those lower than the median as low connectivity. GPA for each student represents their cumulative GPA after their first year at RIT.

Figure 2: Frequency histograms of connectivity level for each GPA level for PHYS majors

In this case, the median connectivity was 1.923 after normalization. Looking at the left skewed plot, as GPA increases, the frequency of students increases. We can also see that high connectivity surpasses low connectivity at the highest GPA interval. This is an interesting observation because, given that a student has a high GPA of 3.5 - 4.0, it is more likely that they were highly connected. The odds ratio is 1.154, which means that the odds of having high connectivity with a high GPA (above 3.0) is more likely than having low connectivity with a high GPA.

Figure 3: Frequency histograms of connectivity level for each GPA level for STAT majors

In this case, the median connectivity was 1.919 after normalization. This plot is also left skewed, with more students receiving a higher GPA. We can also see that while there are slightly more students that had low connectivity at the highest GPA level, there were still more students that had high connectivity at the (3, 3.5] GPA interval. Because we considered 3.0 and above as a high GPA, we can see that connectivity still has a positive impact on these students' GPAs. The odds ratio calculated was 1.140, meaning that the odds of being a highly connected student with a high GPA is more likely than a student receiving a high GPA but having low connectivity.

3.3 Logistic Regression

Figure 4: Plot showing probability of students graduating by connectivity, separated by first generation and continuing generation students in Physics and Statistics/Math.

These plots both depict a positive relationship between connectivity and graduating in 4 years, with coefficients 1.469 for continuing generation (CG) and 0.027 for first generation (FG) students. The connectivity for the CG vs graduation probability relationship was significant with a p-value of 0.00796. The connectivity for FG vs graduation probability was not significantly correlated with a p-value of 0.948. The lack of significance for the FG students could be due to limited data, since fewer students are FG.

Figure 5: Plot showing probability of Physics students graduating by connectivity, separated by CG and FG students.

The CG plot increases probability of graduating slightly as connectivity increases with a coefficient of 0.524, but for the FG plot probability of graduating decreases as connectivity increases with a coefficient of -1.804. Neither of the groups (FG and CG) contained significance in the relationship between graduation rate and connectivity, with p-values of 0.506 for CG and 0.205 for FG.

Figure 6: Plot showing probability of Stat/Math students graduating by connectivity, separated by CG and FG students.

The CG group shows a sharp increase in probability of graduating as connectivity increases from 0 to 1, then stays consistent at close to 100% as connectivity increases. The FG group also has a slight positive relationship, where the rise in probability of graduating is more gradual as connectivity increases. The coefficients are 4.491 for CG and 0.362 for FG. The relationship for CG is significant with a p-value of 0.0175, but is not significant for first gen with a p-value of 0.523.

These findings indicate that there is a positive impact on graduation rates for continuing generation students in particular, however for first generation students we would need more data to conclude any effect that connectivity may have on graduation rates.

Figure 7: Plot showing probability of students graduating by connectivity, separated by male and non-male students in Physics and Statistics/Math.

Due to minimal data for the non-male students, we are unable to conclude any significant relationship. Male students, however, have a significant positive relationship between connectivity and graduation likelihood, with a coefficient of 0.6279 and p-value of 0.0429.

Figure 8: Plot showing probability of Physics students graduating by connectivity, separated by male and non-male students.

Due to minimal data for the non-male physics students, we are unable to conclude any significant relationship. Male physics students show a negative relationship between connectivity and likelihood of graduating with a coefficient of -0.2354 and a p-value of 0.6741 .

Figure 9: Plot showing probability of Statistics/Math students graduating by connectivity, separated by male and non-male students.

Due to minimal data for the non-male statistics/math students, we are unable to conclude any significant relationship. Male statistics/math students, however, have a significant positive relationship between connectivity and graduation likelihood, with a coefficient of 1.1624 and a p-value of 0.0119 .

These findings indicate that connectivity has a positive impact on graduation rates for statistics/math students in particular. However, for non-male students we would need more data to conclude any effect that connectivity may have on graduation rates.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

Overall, our findings suggest connectivity benefits continuing generation and male students, and our results are less conclusive for first generation and non-male students. This supports the need for an increase in underrepresented students, such as non-male and first generation students, in STEM. This is not only to improve the STEM workforce and reduce worker shortages, but also to improve our understanding of what helps these groups of students succeed. Ultimately, a greater understanding of how to encourage and improve representation can lead to combating stereotype threat (Taasobshirazi, 2023). An example of this is the belief that women do not perform as well as men in mathematics (Kapitanoff & Pandey, 2017). Students from traditionally non-minoritized identities, including male and continuing generation students, seem to benefit from connectivity, which supports our hypothesis that connectivity leads to higher retention and graduation rates.

However, we note that an important limitation in our data is its coarse treatment of demographic information. Additionally, another limitation in this research is that it becomes difficult to measure the effect connectivity has on marginalized groups of students due to our small sample size. In the future we may want to incorporate additional cohort terms in order to have a larger sample size for analysis and improve the statistical power of our findings. In addition to improving graduation rate, connectivity seems to have a positive effect on student GPAs. This research offers important new insights into how connectivity impacts student retention.

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